

MOTIVATION AS A TOOL OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *Motivation in teaching is one of the foundations of successful mastery of the subject. In this article, the author examines the approaches of domestic and foreign specialists in the field of psychological and pedagogical aspects of teaching foreign languages. Motivation to study English in educational establishments is defined as a transitional concept, that is, it depends on both the students themselves and the teacher. The paper focuses on ways to form and maintain students' interest in the English language. The author pays attention to both the psychological features of the teacher's work with students, as well as types of tasks that contribute to increasing the motivation of students.*

Keywords: *motivation, tool, learning, foreign, language, teaching, methodology.*

INTRODUCTION

The most effective way to maintain motivation can be considered training built around intrigue and problematic issues. Also the necessity of students' autonomy in the educational process is substantiated in order to develop students' activity and independence. Strategies for forming and maintaining interest in acquiring knowledge can be successfully applied in the practice of teaching foreign languages at a university. Motivation is one of the most important factors in successful learning, and teachers often discuss how they know how to motivate their students. What does this mean? Some try to increase interest in the discipline being studied by making certain demands; someone expresses dissatisfaction with the failure of students, others remain calm; some talk to a group, others to an individual student. Which strategy is more effective? Referring to the educational process, where one of the important components is educational motivation and the motive of teaching, it is appropriate to define these concepts. The motivation of learning is a system of goals, needs and motives that encourage a person to acquire knowledge, skills and methods of cognition, to consciously relate to learning, to be active in educational activities. The motive of teaching is the orientation of the student to various aspects of educational activity, the motivation for active and independent mastery of knowledge and skills. The motive from a psychological point of view is a multidimensional

phenomenon. Therefore, it cannot be interpreted unambiguously, since it is only one of the types of motives, along with needs, goals, aspirations, interests and intentions.

Next, we will focus on the most influential studies of foreign authors in the field of motivation to learn foreign languages.

As it is known, social and cultural factors have an impact on learning a foreign language. Given this fact, Robert Gardner he proposed the most influential theory about motivation to learn a second foreign language. In it, the scientist highlights socio-psychological aspects, since the attitude of students to the language being studied and the community speaking this language strongly influences the desire to learn a particular language. The coexistence of various linguistic (English and French) communities in Canada drew the researcher's attention to the importance of integrative motivation, which implies the desire of students to learn a foreign language based on positive feelings towards a group of people, in particular which is spoken in this language. Gardner also defines instrumental motivation – when a language is studied based on practical considerations, for example, because of the opportunity to get a better job, a high salary or pass an exam.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An important addition to Gardner 's concept can be considered the concept of

“linguistic self-confidence”, introduced by Richard Clement. This term is interpreted by the authors as confidence that a person is able to achieve the set results, achieve goals and competently perform the proposed tasks.

Another significant idea about the structure of educational motivation belongs to American psychologists Edward Desy and Richard Ryan. In they created the theory of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, argues that students interested in academic tasks and results, and receiving pleasure and satisfaction from getting knowledge more likely to be more successful with students than those studying for promotion – good grades, or to avoid punishment on the part of parents or school.

In the early 90s of the XX century, it was suggested that a change in the paradigm of the study of educational motivation and the expansion of motivational concepts in relation to the practice of teaching foreign languages is required. In the early 90s of the XX century, it was suggested that a change in the paradigm of the study of educational motivation and the expansion of motivational concepts in relation to the practice of

teaching foreign languages is required. Thus, the results of Clement's research showed that integrative motivation, “linguistic self-confidence” and the educational atmosphere are the most influential factors, which also confirmed the importance of further psychological and pedagogical research.

Significant contribution to the study of motivation to study a foreign language was introduced by a British scientist of Hungarian origin Zoltan Dernei. He expanded the focus of studying this issue and proposed a more complex structure of motivation to learn a foreign language. He identifies three levels of motivation: the level of language (culture, society, intellectual and pragmatic values), the level of the student

(individual characteristics of the student“ "linguistic self-confidence ") and the level of the educational situation (components related to the course of study itself - programs, teaching materials, methods, tasks, components affecting the personality of the teacher – his behavior, style and practice of conducting classes). Z. Dernei also draws attention to another important feature of educational motivation - instability and change over time. This means that it changes over the entire time of learning a foreign language.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The concept of motivating teaching of a second foreign language by Zoltan Derne and was taken as a basis, where he identified four successive stages: the creation of basic motivational conditions, the generation of initial motivation, the maintenance of motivation, the formation of a positive attitude towards academic performance among students [23, p. 524]. Let's look at each of them and back them up with examples from educational practice.

1. Creation of basic motivational conditions

This includes the proper behavior of the teacher, a pleasant and supportive atmosphere in the classroom, a cohesive study group with acceptable standards of behavior. To implement this approach in practice, the teacher should give students their own example of interest in their subject. The personality of the teacher, his passion for the subject play a very important role, especially in the initial courses. It is unlikely that a student will be able to get full knowledge from a teacher who knows his subject perfectly well, but is burdened by his work. In addition, it is extremely important to establish a good relationship with students, which implies trust and mutual understanding. All kinds of information posted on the bulletin board are suitable for this, for example, a teacher's greeting, a birthday greeting or a successful defense of a project in

English. This will help the students themselves to show their achievements in various subjects. Also , social networks can serve as a platform for communication between a teacher and a student, and mutual assistance. Let's add to the above that the study group as a whole has a powerful influence on its members and even can largely determine the individual preferences of each student [23, p. 527]. A group acquires motivational value when it consists of cohesive people. Therefore, the role of the teacher in creating such a team is especially important. The organization

of a friendly unified "team" of students can, for example, facilitate the exchange of information about each other, the history of the group, that is, when students are connected by common memories, encouragement by the teacher of group assignments, extracurricular activities (trips to cinema, museums, theaters) or overcoming difficulties together (whether it's difficult tasks or passing a difficult exam). Thus, a friendly atmosphere in the group can have a beneficial effect on the motivation of each student.

2. Generation of initial motivation

In this case, such aspects as the creation of a positive image of a community speaking a particular language, respect for the language and culture itself, and the orientation of students to success are important. The motivation to learn a new language is also determined by the specifics themselves the subject. It is well known that any language is something more than communication and is part of the cultural heritage of the people who speak it. Accordingly, the desire to comprehend a foreign language can be influenced by the attitude to culture, traditions, and people who use it. Such cultural conditionality can influence both positively (when the student is interested in the culture of the country) and negatively (when this culture is not accepted) on the motivation of teaching.

Thus, for example, Zoltan Dernei talks about the unsuccessful experience of studying the Russian language under the influence of a negative attitude to culture. For ten years, he barely mastered the alphabet [21, p. 14]. Thinking in this way, the teacher should actively increase the positive attitude of students to the language and culture being studied. In the case of the language of international communication, which is English, the situation is different. So, a teacher can appeal to the well-known and immutable fact that English has become the official language in many areas – in the international academic community, business, tourism. In the modern world, knowledge of this language is necessary for future study abroad, building a successful career, doing business, traveling, and the like.

3. Maintaining motivation

Taking into account the fact that motivation is characterized by variability and impermanence, the teacher needs to resort to a number of actions, such as: creating a pleasant and stimulating learning process, offering tasks that arouse interest in students, maintaining their positive social image, encouraging their autonomy, forming and maintaining the image of a "possible Self" within the framework of the theory of Z. Dernei "motivational self-image system in the context of learning a foreign language" (L2 motivational self system) and, of course, promote close cooperation between students. In the aspect of "home reading", when choosing works, it is important to take into account that they are relevant to the students' experience and relevant to various aspects of their lives. It is desirable that

the book addresses the problems that the current generation of students is facing or may face. The key point is the ability to appeal to your own experience, make projections on your life and thereby express it in your speech.

One example is the novel "Reluctant fundamentalist" by the American writer of Pakistani origin Mohsin Hamid (2007). The main character of the work is a young

Pakistani Genghis who comes to The United States from Pakistan to realize the

"American dream" and regain for themselves and their families the position of middle-class people lost at home. To do this, he studies hard at Princeton University and, after graduating with honors, gets a job at a prestigious company as a financial analyst. The author shows the thorny path of a young Pakistani in American society, notes the impact of the events of September 11, 2001 on the course of world politics, and also puts Genghis before a difficult choice between America and his country. Having discussed in detail the training materials used, let's return to the strategies for maintaining motivation. So, in order to maintain a positive social image in students, conditions are needed where they could show their talents and show their strengths. A good way to implement this strategy can be considered dramatizations or performances in which each student can be given the role of the main character in turn.

4. Formation of students' positive attitude to academic performance

It is well known that the way students relate to their past academic achievements largely determines their future approach to completing tasks. It may seem strange, but their assessment of their own academic performance depends not

only on the absolute, objective indicator of their success, but also on the subjective interpretation of these results. Using appropriate strategies, a teacher can help his students see their academic performance in a more positive way to get more satisfaction from success and progress in studies, as well as to find a constructive explanation for failures. The mistakes made should not "stifle" the initiatives of students.

Therefore, the right approach is chosen by those teachers who do not use a red pen or pencil when checking notebooks, since it is very unpleasant for a person to get a job that is full of bright corrections and immediately gives a signal that the result is unsatisfactory. That is, it is already visually possible to negatively adjust the student. While corrections with a simple pencil do not differ so much from the text written with a pen and therefore will not cause a strong negative reaction. It is even worth going from the opposite and emphasizing not only mistakes, but, for example, well-expressed thoughts in an essay, the correct translation of a sentence if it is complex. Thus, students

see that the teacher is not only the person who notes mistakes, but also the one who is able to notice and appreciate both the abilities of students and the originality of thought.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, the level of motivation not only characterizes the trainees, but also the teacher, that is, this is what motivates students for any activity. A teaching assistant can open up “new horizons” or prospects for students when mastering a foreign language. Also, during the long-term interaction of the teacher and the student, some personal qualities of the latter may change. It follows from this that motivation is a transitional concept. Moreover, it is dynamic, that is, it can change over time, especially in cases of long-term study of a foreign language and needs to be maintained. Understanding the concept of motivating teaching and its subsequent application in the practice of teaching a foreign language can significantly increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

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